

"EFFECTIVENESS OF TREATING HANDALAK SEEDS WITH THE BIOLOGICAL PREPARATION GUMIMAKS"

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Abstract. *The use of biological agents that control growth increases the adaptability of plants to external environmental factors. When treated with the biological product Gumimax, one can observe that seed germination accelerates, the flowering of the first cotyledon, the first paternal and maternal flowers, and the timing of fruit ripening are accelerated. Under the influence of humimaks, productivity indicators increase, as well as the length of the main flower, an increase in the number of lateral branches and the total length of the stem.*

Key words: *khandalak, humimaks, yield, shelf life, seed treatment, main stem, lateral branches, flower, motherhood, fatherhood.*

Research Methods:

The experiments were conducted based on the following methods and methodological guidelines:

- *Methodology of Field Experiments in Vegetable Growing* (Litvinov S.S., Moscow, 2011)
- *Methodology of Field Experiments* (B.A. Dospekhov, 1985)
- *Guidelines for the Testing of Vegetable Crops and Fodder Root Crops* (Moscow, 1982)
- *Methodology for Conducting Experiments in Vegetable, Melon, and Potato Crops* (SPEvaKITI, 2023)

The biochemical composition of fruits from promising *handalak* (melon) variety samples was determined at the Central Chemical-Technological Laboratory of the State Variety Testing Center.

Currently, there is a global trend toward the widespread use of biological preparations in agriculture. A vivid example is the fact that 50–80% of tomato-growing areas are treated with biological agents.

Optimizing the nutrient regime of cultivated plants requires not only the use of organic and mineral fertilizers but also the application of complex fertilizers enriched with micro- and macroelements. Such fertilizers enhance plants' resistance to environmental stress factors (Stupin A.S., 2019; Mitrofanov S.V., Novikov N.N., Nikitin V.S., et al., 2019).

Researchers at the Volga Institute of Ecological and Reclamation Technologies—Abezin V.G., Karpukhin V.V., and Saldayev A.I.—developed and patented a method of treating watermelon seeds with growth regulators. In this method, seeds were soaked in a saline solution of bishofit ($\text{MgCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$) for 0.5–1.5 minutes under a working pressure of 0.15–0.25 MPa. The temperature of the saline solution ranged from 60 to 110°C (source).

Research Results:

In our study, we investigated the effectiveness of treating *handalak* (melon) seeds with the biological preparation *Gumimaks*. According to the data presented in Table 1, treatment with *Gumimaks* resulted in earlier seed germination across all variants—1 to 2 days earlier compared to the control.

Results and Discussion:

In the control variant, initial seed germination was observed on day 8. In the second variant, germination occurred one day earlier, while in the third and fourth variants, germination occurred one day earlier compared to the control.

The emergence of the first true leaves in all variants treated with the biological preparation *Gumimaks* was observed two days earlier than in the control.

A noticeable difference was observed among the variants in the duration from germination to the flowering of male and female flowers. In the variant where seeds were soaked in *Gumimaks* for 6 hours, the first male flowers bloomed one day earlier than the control. In the 9- and 12-hour soaking variants, male flowering occurred three days earlier. The duration of this period in the control was 31 days, while in the 6-hour soaking variant it was 30 days, and in the 9- and 12-hour variants it was 28 days.

The duration from germination to full male flowering was 37 days in the control, 33 days in the 6-hour variant, and 30 days in both the 9- and 12-hour soaking variants. In other words, full male flowering occurred 4 days earlier in the second variant, and 7 days earlier in the third and fourth variants compared to the control.

A similar trend was observed in the duration from germination to both the initial and full flowering of female flowers. In the control variant, the time from germination to the first appearance of female flowers was 36 days. In the second variant, this duration was 34 days, and in the third and fourth variants, it was reduced to 32 days.

The duration from germination to full flowering of female flowers was 41 days in the control, 37 days in the second variant, and 35 days in the third and fourth variants. Thus, this period was shortened by 4 days in the second variant and by 6 days in the third and fourth variants compared to the control.

Pre-sowing seed treatment with *Gumimaks* also had a significant impact on the duration from germination to fruit ripening. The time from germination to the beginning of fruit ripening was reduced by 2 days in the second variant, and by 3 days in the third and fourth variants compared to the control. Full ripening occurred 3 days earlier in the second and third variants, and 4 days earlier in the fourth variant.

Overall, pre-sowing treatment of *handalak* seeds with the biological preparation *Gumimaks* significantly influenced the duration of developmental phases. In all experimental variants, the growth periods were shorter than in the control, especially in the third and fourth variants, where the effects were most pronounced.

Additionally, pre-sowing seed treatment with *Gumimaks* had a significant effect on the biometric parameters of *handalak* plants.

In all experimental variants, the length of the main stem was significantly greater compared to the control. While the main stem length in the control variant was 135.5 cm, it ranged from 139.5 to 143.0 cm in the treated variants. This corresponds to 103.7% to 105.5% relative to the control.

A similar trend was observed in the total length of the main stem and lateral branches combined.

The *Gumimaks* preparation also contributed to an increase in the number of lateral branches in *handalak* plants. In the control variant (seeds untreated), the number of lateral branches averaged 3.5 per plant. In the variants treated with *Gumimaks*, the number ranged from 3.9 to 4.1 branches per plant. This represents an increase of 111.4% to 117.1% compared to the control.

Effect on Fruit Yield and Quality:

Treatment with the *Gumimaks* preparation also led to a slight increase in the number of fruits per plant, as shown in Table 3. In the control and the second experimental variant, the number of fruits per plant was the same. However, in the third and fourth variants, the fruit number increased to 3.2 fruits per plant, which is 103.2% relative to the control.

A slight increase in fruit weight was also observed under the influence of *Gumimaks*. In the control variant, the average fruit weight was 0.87 kg, while in the third and fourth experimental variants, it increased to 0.9 kg, equating to 103.4% of the control.

As a result, the treatment of *handalak* seeds with *Gumimaks* positively influenced both yield and fruit quality. The highest total yield was recorded in the third and fourth variants, amounting to 41.7 t/ha. In these variants, the total yield was 106% compared to the control.

The highest marketable yield was also observed in the same variants, ranging from 39.0 to 39.4 t/ha, which corresponds to 107.7%–108.8% compared to the control.

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